

METHOD AND TECHNIQUES OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: Analysis of similarities between procedures, strategies and methods of translation and identify available second language acquisition theories, clarify importance of translation in language learning and using translation as a language teaching and learning tool.

Key words: Methodology, translation, literal translation, communicative translation, word for word translation, faithful translation, semantic translation, free translation, idiomatic translation.

To carry out an adequate translation, you need to know special methods and techniques of translation, which determine one or another method of translation. Methods, techniques and methods of translation vary by the translator depending on the type and unit of translation. But the method of translation is the fundamental and classifying category of translation, since it is based on the basic laws speech- thinking activity of the translator. Reception and method, in turn, act as derivatives of the method of translation. Translation method is a system of translation operations aimed at to achieve a specific goal of translation activity. Such a system operations is an objectively existing regularity, reflecting the features of the speech and thought activity of the translator. Modern science knows only two methods of translation, both objectively existing patterns of transition from one language to another. Signed method of translation - translation operations are carried out at the formal level. Literal translation of a word, phrase or a whole sentence in a certain context allows you to save the adequacy of the translated material.

The principle is premised in this method is that the mastery of foreign languages learned that can be achieved by exercises translation of languages taught in the mother tongue of students. The exercise of this translation is the main exercise in this method. In their attempt to distinguish between methods, strategies, and techniques, Methods of translation are defined as the way of a particular translation process that is carried out in terms of translator's objective, i.e, a global option that affects the whole texts and their definition is strengthened by Newmark stating that “translation methods relate to whole text while translation procedures are used sentences and the smaller units of language”. It can be concluded that the result of translated texts is determined by the methods of translation used by translators because the aim and the intention of

translators will affect the overall result of their translated texts. Newmark draws the methods of translation in the form of a diagram dividing them into SL emphasis such as word-for-word translation, literal translation, faithful translation, as well as semantic translation, and TL emphasis such as adaptation, free translation, idiomatic translation, as well as communicative translation.

Source: Newmark: 1988

Word-for-Word translation method is used on the pre-translation phase where the TL words are directly put below the SL words as so called interlinear translation. Cultural words are translated literally out of the context. Translators only need to find the equivalent words from SL to TL but the position of those SL words remains intact in TL to understand the mechanism of TL and as Catford states: “to illustrate in a crude way differences structure between SL and TL for further studies”. Word for word method is less frequently used because the translator tries to understand the mechanics and find the equivalent word from source language or to construe a difficult text as a pre translation process.

Literal translation method of translation is between word-for-word and free translation where the words are still translated out of context as in word-for-word translation but then they are placed based on the grammatical structure of TL. The SL grammatical forms are converted to their nearest target language equivalent.

However, the lexical words are translated out of context. Literal translation method is the source language grammatical forms that are converted to their nearest target language equivalent. Literal translation method is more frequently used because the translator tries to keep the meaning in the source language converts construction of the source language into intended construction of the target language.

In **faithful translation**, translators try to reproduce the contextual meaning of SL to TL and place them based on the grammatical structure of TL. Cultural words are translated but its grammatical and lexical abnormality still occurs. Faithful here means the translation attempt to be completely faithful to the intentions and text-realization of the SL writer. Faithful translation tries to reproduce the precise contextual meaning of the original within the constraint of the target language grammatical structures. It

transfers cultural words and faithfully follows the source language grammatical forms. The method is used to reproduce the precise contextual meaning of the original within the constraint of grammatical structures in the target language.

Semantic translation method of translation produces a more natural translation than the previous method since in semantic translation, the aesthetic element is taken into consideration and cultural words in SL are translated into its cultural equivalent in TL. Semantic translation is more flexible than faithful translation which is stated as an uncompromising and dogmatic method. The semantic method of translation - involves a preliminary identification of a denotation with subsequent searches for a foreign equivalent. The translator is forced to realize the semasiological connections of the sign (morphemes, words, phrases, etc.) of the target language within the given context, then to determine in general the designated speech situation, the communicative task of the given sign in the context, and pick up.

Method of adaptation as the freest form of translation is commonly used in translating poetries and script of plays where cultural conversions occur from source language to target language without changing the themes, characters, or plot of SL. Therefore, if translators want to adapt a script of play, for example, they have to maintain the characters and plot of the script while adapting only its dialogues from source language to target language. Method is used reproduce for the deplorable practice of having a poem or play literally translated and then rewritten by an established dramatist or poet has reproduced much poor adaptation, but other adaptation has “rescued” period plays.

In **free translation** method, the source text content takes more priority than its form so paraphrase is commonly used to assure the message from source text can be clearly delivered to the readers of target text. It is reproducing the matter or the context without the form of original. Free translation method is reproducing the matter or the context without the form of the original. Compared to literal translation, due to the reason of preserving mainly the message of source language not the construction or style.

When translators reach **idiomatic translation** method, their translations will not sound like translated texts anymore since in this method, the message is reproduced in TL with more natural and familiar expressions sometimes using colloquialisms and idioms which do not exist in SL. The method reproduces the message of the source text but tend to distort nuances of meaning by preferring colloquialism and idioms.

Communicative translation method prioritizes the elements of communication such as purpose of translation and readership, so translators have to translate the contextual meaning of source language both its language and its content to be acceptable and understandable for readers of target language who expect no difficulties in reading translated texts.

Based on Hilaire Belloc, there are six general rules for the translator of prose texts, they are:

1. The translator should avoid his works word by word or sentence by sentence, but should instead tackle the work as an overall unit and keep in mind the whole sense of the work when carrying out his translation.

2. The translator should render idiom by idiom and idiom of their nature demand translation into another from that of the original.

3. The translator should be rendered into an equivalent target language intention, and as the weight that a given source language, expression may have is often different from the weight of its counterpart in the target language (stronger or could be weaker) if it translated literally the translator might find it necessary to add words to make up for the difference.

4. The translator should avoid the pitfall of similar word in different languages, for example of the sign „brutal“ which signifies „serious“ in French but has different denotation in English.

5. The translator is advised to transmute boldly; Belloc suggest that the essence of translating is „the resurrection of an alien thing in a native body“

6. The translator should never embellish. He does stress the need for the translator to consider the prose texts as a structured whole whilst language. He accepts that there is a moral responsibility to the original, but feels that the translator process in order to provide the target language stylistic and idiomatic norms.

Translation techniques are defined in many books as procedures to analyse and classify how translation equivalence works. There are many translation techniques explained by experts. Scholars share their view on translation techniques as follows. Borrowing is a translator borrows some words or idiom from source language. There are two kind of borrowing, pure borrowing and naturalized borrowing. In calque the translator translates the phrase in source language literally. Literal translation is when the translator translates the source language word by word. Transposition is the process when the translator adjusts the word structures or shifts the word classes. Adaptation replaces the element of source language culture with the same element in the target language culture, and the target language is familiar to the target readers. Amplification paraphrases implicit information in source language. Generalization uses a neutral or general terminology in target language (from subordinate to super ordinate). Particularization uses more concrete or precision terms. This technique is the opposite of generalization technique. Modulation is when the translator changes the point of view, focus or cognitive category in relevance with the source language. Reduction partially omits information of source text in target text. Translator may delete the word or information in the source language. Both deletion and reduction techniques are omitting some words, but there is a difference between deletion and

reduction. Deletion technique omits the whole information, while the reduction only omits the information partially. Addition adds more information to clarify the concept in source language to the target readers. Variation changes the linguistic or paralinguistic elements which affect the linguistic variation such as dialect, language style, etc.

The method of using the notes in consecutive interpreting plays an important role. It is based on fixing on paper the memory reference points identified as a result of semantic analysis. Such records are effective if they are produced in the most economical way that represents a single system. The system of records is already selected semantic reference points is composed of abbreviated alphabetic notation, symbols and their vertical arrangement. It is based on the semantic analysis of the statement.

Abbreviated alphabetic notation is the process of semantic analysis of the utterance, singles out semantic strongholds from the perceived speech flow. Some of them he designates with words, which he writes in letters. Unabbreviated notation of words consisting of more than four or five letters, the translator, as a rule, cannot afford. With abbreviated alphabetic notation, the most important thing is to determine which letters disappear from the written words will not interfere with reading these words. It is quite clear that any first letter of any word should be written as the original code sign that determines the direction of perception. The letters in their combinations are independent, and the entry of the first letter narrows the choice of the next one.

The text segmentation method is used in written translation, especially when translating works of art. It involves dividing the statement into fragments of various sizes and translating each of the selected fragments. The division of the text depends on the volume of the text, such as information contained in it, and the form of its submission. Traditionally, a finished statement is divided into an introductory, main and final part. Within each of them, the translator determines the main idea, fundamental arguments, etc. A special place is occupied by the translation of direct or indirect speech, which also stands out as an independent fragment of the translation. In each of the fragments, the translator identifies the speech task, the communicative task, the context and its levels.

The method of establishing formal sign relationships is used in simultaneous translation. They are mastered by experienced translators. It is based on the speech-thinking mechanism of proactive synthesis, which allows a professional translator to recognize language units with anticipation of the entire statement at the sentence level. Linguistic intuition and linguistic conjecture, deep background knowledge, knowledge of the conditions of communication, participants in communication, etc. also play an important role. The specificity of translation actions in simultaneous translation is in the following:

- 1) the object of orientation is reduced from the whole statement to its separate part;
- 2) the translator has incomplete ideas about the semantic structure of the utterance translated into rhythmic groups;
- 3) the set of guidelines necessary for making a decision on the lexical and grammatical organization of an utterance in the target language is insufficient;
- 4) the adoption of a translation decision on the grammatical structure and lexical content of only part of the statement, as well as the question of their further deployment and completion, remains open until orientation in the components of the statement.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language", Tashkent, 2019, October 21.
2. Delisle, Jean/Woods worth, Judith (1995). *Translators through History*. Amsterdam: J.Benjamins Publishing /Unesco Publishing. P. – 87.
3. Eugene Nida. *Toward a Science of Translating. With Special Reference to Principles and Procedures Involved in Bible Translating*. Leiden. 1964. P. – 28.
4. Katharina, R. (1971) *Type, Kind and Individuality of Text: Decision Making in Translation*. In: Venuti, L., Ed., *The Translation Studies Reader*, Routledge, London, P. 160-171.
5. Holmes, James S. (1988): *Translated! Papers on Literary Translation and Translation Studies*. Ed. by Raymond van den Broek. Amsterdam: Rodopi. P. – 65.
6. Toury, Gideon. 1995. *Descriptive Translation Studies and Beyond*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: J.Benjamins.
7. Snell-Hornby, M. (1988) *Translation Studies: An Integrated Approach*. John Benjamins, Amsterdam and Philadelphia. P. – 24.
8. Hans-J.-Verme... Hans J. Vermeer (1996). *A Scopus Theory of Translation*. P. – 65.
9. Christiane Nord. *Text Analysis in Translation. Theory, Method, and Didactic Application of a Model for Translation-Oriented Text Analysis*. 1991. P. – 88.
10. Tymoczko, Maria. 2006. *Enlarging Translation, Empowering Translators*. Manchester: St. Jerome. P. – 7.
11. Otaboboyeva, F. (2023). Psychological, Pedagogical and methodological foundation of foreign language of lerners' intercultural competence. *International scientific research journal*.
12. Otaboboyeva, F. (2024). COMMUNICATIVE AND PRAGMATIC COMPONENTS OF INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE. *Interpretation and researches*, 2(1 (23)).
13. Otaboboyeva, F. (2022). The essence of the work of Gerge Orwell" Animal farm" and its impact on people. *Scientific methodological journal*.